

Managing Outreach on Open Research Material to Heterogeneous Groups

The CACTUS Scale and Labels as a Method of Mapping Target Groups Based on Their Skill Level and Interests

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Problem: For various open science initiatives, providing researchers with adequate resources to develop their projects has always been a priority. However, in practice, many initiatives have found that researchers face different kinds of situations that prevent them from progressing as they would like, despite having the resources available. Especially finding the material one specifically needs in the vast sea of offerings can be a challenge. In the worst-case scenario, researchers shy away from Open Research at all because they feel lost or overstimulated. Considering these experiences, appropriately identifying specific needs (beyond simply providing access to open science resources) can help both open science organisations and researchers to make better use of the resources and, consequently, more efficiently bring their projects to fruition. Under this premise, the problem becomes complex, as researchers generate different issues, challenges, and questions depending on multiple conditions, such as: How many years of experience do they have in their field of research? How do they properly utilise open science resources? Do they have full clarity on the path they should follow when conducting research? This project seeks to propose a practical, feasible and clear solution to address these situations.

In this paper, the following definition of research data is used: Anything which helps you formulate or reach your research conclusion is research data. Essentially, it is the evidence or “stuff” collected during your research project that can support and validate your findings.

Main target: Addressing people 1 on 1 is the perfect way to inform about Research Data Management (RDM) and Open Science initiatives because you can adapt to their level of knowledge or their specific interest, but that is impossible to keep up. Therefore, managing outreach to heterogeneous groups is key. We decided to come up with criteria and labels that help people to navigate to what fits their level and interest.

Background: The scale and labels were developed during the [OSPARK Bootcamp](#), organised by [Open Life Science](#) (OLS) and the [Digital Research Academy](#) (DRA) and funded by the European Union, in Belfast/Northern Ireland on April 24 and 25, 2026. It was part of the unconference session, and the authors, open science enthusiasts from India, Hungary, Mexico, Northern Ireland and Germany, formed the group in order to develop the material in a sprint session of approximately 3 hours in total. Everything is published under the CC BY 4.0 Creative Commons License, and the authors encourage further development of the matrix.

Approach:

To find what sort of materials or tutorials would be most helpful for a given researcher, we need to assess the knowledge or experience and the specific interest of the person. The knowledge about digital research should not simply refer to the scientific seniority of the person (i.e. PhD student, postdoc, professor, etc.), as more senior people do not necessarily have more experience in the specific field of digital research.

Hence, we define the various stages of the (Digital) Research Experience Spectrum used to describe where the researcher is at the journey as follows:

- Knowledge Level 0 = You are beginning your journey with digital research.
- Knowledge Level 1 = You know the key terms, and with a companion, you are eager to explore.
- Knowledge Level 2 = You are confident in engaging with digital methods/tools and excited to explore more.
- Knowledge Level 3 = You make your own path in digital research and can teach others.

To help with self-assessment, the knowledge level is defined by 3 questions that are marked by 0/1/2/3 points.

Question 1:

Do you understand what is meant by the term “research data” in the context of your research?

- Not at all = 0
- Kind of =1
- I feel comfortable defining it = 2
- Obviously = 3

Question 2:

Do you have experience using research data?

- Not at all = 0
- Kind of =1
- I feel comfortable using it = 2
- Obviously = 3

Question 3:

Are you confident in explaining research data and its handling to others?

- Not at all = 0
- Kind of =1
- I feel comfortable explaining it = 2

- Obviously = 3

Answer the questions and add the points. The total score defines your knowledge level:

0 to 3 points = Knowledge Level 1

4 to 6 points = Knowledge Level 2

7 to 9 points = Knowledge Level 3

Another dimension we have to take into account is at which stage of the data life cycle the user is. We use the following four stages as parameters for the x-axis (What do you want to do with your data?)

1. **Data collection:** This is the initial stage, the moment when the researcher does not yet have data and must determine their sources of information.
2. **Data preparation:** In this stage, the researcher already has the data but must prepare it before analysis: cleaning, subsetting, correcting, identifying errors, missing values, dealing with invalid values, and some basic descriptive statistics.
3. **Data analysis:** At this stage, the data is ready to generate results. The researcher can now load it into software, e.g. for statistical analysis or modeling. The final results are obtained at this stage.
4. **Data dissemination/publication:** Finally, once the results of the analysis have been generated, the data must be documented and saved in a format that allows the reproducibility of the results. These files can usually be published (if the researcher wishes to do so) along with their project and must include proper metadata.

Based on the self-evaluation (knowledge level and interest), the researcher, on the one hand, can find his or her position on the CACTUS scale. On the other hand, organisations offering material on aspects of open science and research data management can label their output. Thus, both sides can “communicate” to bring researchers and materials together on the level that is just right. In short, the labels give orientation to find materials/information on different topics according to one's knowledge level.

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Continuous Assessment and Capture of Technical and Universal research Skills

Knowledge level 3	Squirrel			
Knowledge level 2	Ant			
Knowledge level 1	Bee			
	Data collection	Data preparation	Data analysis	Data dissemination/ publication

In the final step, the generic emojis were redesigned by Saranjeet Kaur Bhogal:

